

Angelo Leogrande¹

The Income Gap Between Northern and Southern Italy

A citizen of the North has an income expectation of eight thousand euros higher than a citizen of the South.

Istat calculates the value of per capita gross disposable income in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2019.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of per capita gross disposable income in 2019. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first place by value of per capita gross disposable income in 2019 with an amount equal to 24,423 euros, followed by Lombardy with an amount equal to 23,281.90 euros and from Emilia Romagna with an amount equal to 23,041.30 euros. In the middle of the table there are Veneto with an amount equal to 20,746.10 euros, followed by Lazio with an amount equal to 19,998.50 euros and the Marche with an amount equal to 19,206.00 euros. Sicily closes the ranking with an amount equal to 13,826.50 euros, Campania with an amount equal to 13,681.90 euros and Calabria with an amount equal to 13,160.20 euros.

Ranking of the Italian regions by absolute change in the value of per capita gross disposable income in the period 2004-2019. Trentino-Alto Adige ranks first in terms of the absolute change in gross disposable income per capita with an amount equal to 4,159.40 equal to + 20.53%, followed by Veneto with an amount equal to 3,105.20 euros or equal to 17.60%, and from the Marche with a value of 2,943.20 euros. In the middle of the table there are Puglia with an amount equal to € 2,321.10 equal to 19.08%, followed by Emilia Romagna with an amount equal to € 2,314.10 or equal to 11.16% and Piedmont with a amount equal to € 2,275.00 equal to 11.91%. Umbria closes the ranking with an amount equal to 1,513.70 euros equal to 8.70%, Campania with an amount equal to 1,423.90 euros equal to 11.62% and Lazio, in last place, with a value absolute value of € 1,242.60 equal to a growth of 6.63%.

North. The value of per capita gross disposable income in the North increased between 2015 and 2019 from an amount equal to € 20,812.10 up to an amount equal to € 22,366.00 or a change of € 1,553.90 equal to 7, 47%. In the passage between 2015 and 2016, the value of the Gross Disposable Income per Capita abbreviated in GDIPC increased from an amount equal to € 20,812.10 up to a value of € 21,179.80 or equal to a change of 367.70 euro equal to 1.77%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the GDIPC in the North increased from an amount equal to 21,719.80 euros up to a value equal to 21,770.40 euros or equal to a value of 590.60 euros equal to a value of 2, 79%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the GDIPC in the North increased from an amount equal to 21,770.40 euros up to a value equal to 22,197.30 euros or open to a change of 426.90 euros equal to a value of 1.96%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019, the value of the GDIPC increased from an amount equal to € 22,197.30 up to an amount of € 22,366.00 or equal to a value of € 168.70 equal to a value of 0.76 %.

Center. The value of the GDIPC in Central Italy grew between 2015 and 2019 from an amount equal to € 18,828.50 up to a value of € 20,061.20 or a change of € 1,232.70 equal to a value of 6, 55%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the GDIPC in the Center increased from an amount equal to 18,828.50 euros up to a value of 19,128.60 euros or equal to a value of 300.10 euros equal

¹ Ph.D., Assistant Professor of Economics at Lum University Giuseppe Degennaro, and researcher in Economics at LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Statale 100 km 18, Bari, Puglia, Italy. Email: leogrande.cultore@lum.it

to 1.59 %. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the GDIPC increased from an amount equal to € 19,128.60 up to a value of € 19,427.40 or equal to a change of € 298.80 equal to an amount of 1, 56%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the GDIPC in Central Italy increased from an amount equal to 19,427.40 euros up to an amount of 19,845.00 euros or equal to a change of 417.60 euros or equal to an amount of 2.15%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the GDIPC in Central Italy increased from an amount equal to € 19,845.00 up to a value of € 20,061.20 or equal to a change of € 216.20 equal to 1.09%.

South of Italy. The value of the GDIPC in the Mezzogiorno grew between 2015 and 2019 from an amount equal to € 13,266.20 up to a value of € 14,193.30 or equal to a change of € 927.10 equivalent to a value of 6, 99%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the GDIPC increased from an amount equal to 13,266.20 euros up to an amount of 13,437.90 euros or equal to a change of 171.70 euros equal to an amount of 1.29%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the GDIPC increased from an amount equal to 13,437.90 up to an amount equal to 13,660.60 euros or equal to a change of an amount of 222.60 euros equal to an amount of 1.66%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the GDIPC increased from an amount of € 13,660.50 to a value of € 13,909.80 or equal to a change of € 249.30 equal to 1.82%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the GDIPC in the South increased from an amount equal to 13,909.80 euros up to a value equal to 14,193.30 euros or equal to a value of 283.50 euros equal to a value of 2, 04%.

Clusterization. The clustering model was used using the k-Means algorithm to check whether there are classifications within the Italian regions that in any way refer to the central, northern, and southern macro-regions. The optimization of clustering was achieved using the Silhouette coefficient. The following clusters have been identified:

- Cluster 1: Abruzzo, Sardinia, Molise;
- Cluster 2: Sicily, Campania, Calabria, Puglia, Basilicata;
- Cluster 3: Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 4: Veneto, Umbria, Tuscany, Marche, Lazio, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Piedmont.

The sorting of clusters by average value of gross disposable income among the constituent regions sees cluster 3 at the head with an average amount of € 22,847.78, followed by cluster 4 with an amount of € 20,321.66, followed by from cluster 1 with an average value of € 15,600.00 and from cluster 2 with an amount of € 13,914.90. It follows therefore that $C3 > C4 > C1 > C2$.

Synthesis. In conclusion, we can underline that per capita gross disposable income tends to grow in all regions, albeit to varying degrees. Certainly, the South is below the national average. The southerners in 2019 produced a per capita gross disposable income of 14 thousand euros, 5 thousand euros lower than the per capita gross disposable income in Italy of 19 thousand euros. None of the southern regions manages to reach the value of the Italian per capita gross disposable income. The cluster analysis shows a dominance of the central-north regions which is contrasted with the weakness of the income of the central-southern regions. In short, the gap between North and South tends to grow prospectively. In 2004 the difference between the GDIPC of the North and the GDIPC of the South was equal to a value of € 7,382.20, while in 2019 the same difference reached € 8,172.70, an increase of € 790.50 equal to 10.70%. It follows that a citizen of the North has a per capita income expectation of about 8,000 euros higher than a citizen of the SOUTH. Economic policies of territorial cohesion should target the DRLPC gap to create greater equality of opportunity and increase GDP at the country level. The idea of a two-speed country is no longer sustainable in the current European and international context, which requires activism of productions, technological innovations, international openings, and business readiness in public-private participation.

Declarations

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